

A Review of Recent Use of Vision Processing Devices in Image Identification and Real-World Applications

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Abstract--Vision processing devices are need of real time and offline applications. The review of these devices usage in real world applications are discussed while considering actual usage, their performance and evaluation metrics, advantages and limitations. A diversified exploration of hardware device NCS 2 is presented in this review. Discussion on the contents, limitations and future applications are also mentioned.

Keywords---Neural Computing Stick, NCS 2, Real Time, Performance Evaluation, Inference, Edge AI, Prediction, Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Computational imaging devices and their capabilities are discussed in [1]; like Google's Project Tango, however more about architecture of such vision processors is discussed therein. The challenge to work with image processing and computer vision in pipeline is the key requirement [2]. Pest detection in agriculture is done using OpenCV blob detector, task-wise power assessment is also mentioned [3]. In [4], a low-cost person detection is done using Raspberry Pi 3 B+ using, SSD (Single-Shot object Detection) and YOLO (You Only Look Once) algorithms. In this project report, sensing distance, accuracy-speed trade-off, how object size impact on model detection ability is discussed. Further it is mentioned that power efficiency is of utmost importance is mobile applications such as streaming (sequences of events in time); and many technological architectural details are discussed. Bidirectional people moving in and out- head counting real time system is discussed in [5] using two video frames. Neural network layer pruning is a technique used to reduce the latency and computation cost of transformer models by removing redundant layers or heads while maintaining

performance. Single layer pruning using NCS, CPU, GPU is discussed their in. Edge AI consists of real-time computations locally on an embedded system and detail features comparison between four different hardware is mentioned in [6] one of which is peak performance in GFLOPS. Similar kind of comparison is done in [6], while handling challenges variations in illumination, viewpoint, scale, occlusion, and background clutter. Considering safety and accidents into account, identification of foreign object detection is done in metro screen doors in [7]. Anchor-free object detection algorithms which avoids time consuming and inefficient classification of object location and that is exploited in [7]. Experimental pest identification using AI and the Internet of Things is done in [8]. Average accuracy is calculated using ten different angle images of pests. Location of the pests is also sent to farmers through mobile phones. In [9], a variety of custom deep learning classifiers are designed and optimized for the embedded deployment and benchmarked against baseline classifiers. NCS 2 inference engine accepts and understands only the Intermediate Representation (IR) model, however to generate an IR model from trained CNN model OpenVINO Toolkit is essential along with weight, and bias values tuning [10]. Industry view of Edge computing is the topic of [11]. The concept of Edge is very well discussed along with numeric values of latencies involved in end to end communication service providers such as devices – drones, video cameras, data centres, and cloud. Reference [12] is an application in disaster management with dataset captured by satellite. Use of NCS is explored as coprocessor with Intel Xeon processor. Prediction of damaged and undamaged areas almost instantaneously is mentioned; however best results can be obtained with batch data. Further inference performance is also discussed based on

parameters – processing time, latency and throughput. Many of the works shows performance evaluation of CNN or other models, parameters such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score are utilised. Precision shows the ability to label the sample as truly positive (0 and 1). Recall implies percentage of the positive samples correctly classified (0 and 1). The F1 score value is between 0 and 1, and it is a harmonic mean of precision and recall (0 and 1). In [13], use of NCS 2 for medical image segmentation is explored. Usage of modified U-Net model with NCS 2 is further discussed. It is pointed out that the purpose of NCS 2 is to facilitate the computation and accelerate the machine learning model's inference over edge devices via providing profiling, tuning and compiling a deep neural network. Reference [14] is a high-end application – satellite Earth observation. It discusses AI processing engine Myriad 2 (Vision Processing Unit) VPU and it performs all EoT (Eyes of Things- an international project funded by European Union) processing and control. Images are submitted to Myriad for inference. The detail inference steps are shown further. While pixel-wise accuracy is an indication of quality of inference, it is pointed in [14] that actual index of quality is False Positive (FP) rate. Fine defects on glass screen surface as small as 13 μm are identified offline using YOLOv3, Faster RCNN and SSD are discussed along with details of network structure of U-Net. [15]. Two devices are irradiated with high energy protons: Google Coral Accelerator Module and Intel NCS 2 in [16]. Their post irradiation analysis is discussed further. In [17] it is mentioned that different hardware devices and multiple NCS 2 can work with Windows, Linux, MacOS, or Raspbian. It is further remarked that in case where both power consumption and performance are taken into account, multiple combinations of NCS are better than Central Processing Unit (CPU-i7-5950HQ). Comparative analysis of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) based analysis using YOLO, MobileNetV2 and more are discussed with applications like steel surfaces, rail tracks (real time detection), textiles and displays [19]. It also put emphasis on need of hardware-based benchmarks in real time applications. Medical application of subretinal surgery using CNN and real time tracking control using Model Predictive Control (MPC) is discussed in [20]. Experimental results are given using deep network-based tool trip predictions with ResNet-18 as encoder and U-net as decoder.

II. DISCUSSIONS

The introduction provides a comprehensive overview of cutting-edge technologies in computational imaging, edge AI, and embedded systems, showcasing a wide range of applications. It highlights the importance of real-time

inference and power efficiency, which are crucial for modern mobile and embedded AI systems. The inclusion of hardware comparisons, like NCS 2 and Raspberry Pi 3 B+, is valuable for readers making decisions about AI deployment on edge devices. The references to various successful use cases, such as pest detection and foreign object identification, demonstrate the practical potential of these technologies. The focus on neural network optimization techniques, such as pruning, aligns well with current trends in optimizing models for efficiency and performance. By exploring the intersection of AI models, hardware, and real-world challenges, the passage captures the interdisciplinary nature of modern AI applications.

III. LIMITATIONS, CRITICS AND PROPOSED APPLICATIONS

Technical terms like YOLO, SSD, and NCS 2 are need to be identified in depth as it is not possible to go in depth here. It is further possible to discuss the real-world impact of model optimization techniques like pruning and hardware comparisons. The evaluation metrics (accuracy, precision, recall) are mentioned however their connection to practical trade-offs like latency, throughput, and power consumption may be further explored. We suggest applications in which these hardware devices can be used: Wildlife Conservation and Poaching Detection. Monitoring endangered species and preventing poaching in wildlife reserves or protected areas using real-time AI-powered video analytics. NCS 2 can be used using cameras with integrated AI accelerators, real-time analysis can be performed to detect illegal activities (e.g., poaching, traps, or unauthorized human presence) or monitor endangered species in their natural habitat. Further Computer vision algorithms can identify specific animals or humans from camera feeds and trigger alarms or alerts to authorities in case of suspicious activity. This will result in benefit such as improved protection of wildlife by enabling proactive monitoring with minimal energy consumption and low-latency response. Another application: Real-Time Border Surveillance and Illegal Entry Detection. Monitoring national borders, entry points, and other sensitive areas (seaports, airports) to detect illegal crossings and unregistered entries in real-time. NCS 2 can help: Cameras and drones equipped with NCS 2 can be used to monitor large border areas, employing computer vision to detect unusual movement patterns, suspicious behaviours, using object detection algorithms (e.g., YOLO, Faster R-CNN). NCS 2 can identify people or vehicles that have crossed into restricted areas or breached border fences. It can also detect unauthorized boats or vehicles at sea or in remote border regions. Benefit: no human surveillance is required, reducing the time to act and preventing illegal entry before

it occurs. The details of comparison are mentioned in Table I at the end of the paper. This idea is discussed in section IV.

We also propose use of such vision processing unit in real time object part identification in future. Manufacturing process cycle time will be of utmost importance and hence cycle time, object size, feature extraction, selection of model will be crucial.

IV. PROPOSED APPLICATION WITH MORE DETAILS

We propose use of NCS 2 to identify activities from illegal migrants, who already has crossed country boarder and staying at roads; specifically, near traffic signals spaces in cities. It is identified that there exists a strong network of peoples in country who support such kind of illegal migrants to be stable in the country by helping them in a direct way. These ways are multi-folds. These migrants are allotted flowers, or seasonal occasional gift items such as caps to sell at traffic signals. These people do beg to people in vehicles for money, water and food. Their children of very small age randomly walk on signals thus creating danger of accidents. They further cook on roads-aside and throw waste on foot-paths. They also occupy illegal vehicles like three wheeled auto-rickshaw. Second way how these people are supported by some group: someone from the (illegal) supporting group provides them money in cash. Problem formulation: identification of such events where a large number of cash is given to these illegal immigrants, identification of peoples who supports such events, identification of their vehicles with number plate identification, identification of location at such transactions with the help of cameras in real time. This will require high end video analytics with scene understanding with feature extractions. Ideal assumption of camera for this application is BIT-RC2075W Long Range HD Network Laser Night Vision PTZ Camera. A different kind of intrusion detection and use of video analytics can be identified in [21]; however, our application is entirely different that the one discussed in [21]. We further propose methodology for proposed work: machine learning-based methodology to classify events identifications. Machine learning methodology in [21] are CNN, Random Forest, Vision transformer. These models further provide an important property like equivariance [22]. This property of CNN significantly improve accuracy and robustness of identification against noise and interferences [23]. To extract text form images OCR (Optical Character Recognition) is most utilized technique. One of the advance models in analytics is TASK-ORIENTED COMMUNICATION WITH TEMPORAL ENTROPY CODING (TOCOM-TEM) in [24]. The engineering working principle behind task-relevant feature extraction from each frame and develop a fusion module at the server

to collectively pull the current received features with the previous features to perform inference is deterministic information bottle-neck principle which is mentioned in [24]. One of the challenges issues in such application is complexity within communication overhead and the latency.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The immense potential of edge AI devices like NCS 2 in a wide range of real-world use cases. From wildlife conservation and border security to disaster management and smart agriculture, these devices are at the forefront of enabling real-time, energy-efficient processing of complex data streams in resource-constrained environments. As AI algorithms and edge devices continue to evolve, even more transformative applications in these critical sectors are expected.

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Table I Comparison of works

Year	First Author	Application	Work related to	Hardware used / discussed	Advantages	Limitation	Image size pixels	Training, Validation, Test Images
[1]	Fergal Connor,	Augmented Reality	Vision processor design challenges	Myriad2	real-time support for low-latency computer vision (less than 2 μ s)	Application processor typical performance within thermal and battery limits: 400 Gbytes/s	NA	NA
[2]	Oscar Deniz et. Al.	QR code, text , face detection, motion detection, emotion recognition	Technical usage of hardware and software	EoT DevBoard, Movidius devel. board	EoT:Low power consumption and little overhead(2 bytes), uses TCP/IP stack and MQTT protocol	In context to EoT device library: JPEG not supported, reading/writing of sqlite3 files not supported	500 X 500, 400 X 300, 50 X 50,	-
[3]	Davide Brunelli et. Al.	Pest detection in Precision agriculture	Image Processing And deep Learning	Movidius NCS and Raspberry Pi 3	Average power consumption is minimal because of low duty cycle	-	112 x 112	-
[4]	Adam Gunnarsson	Person detection	Object detection	Raspberry Pi 3 B+	Low cost	Object detection is very slow	224 x 224, 160 x 160, 96 x 96	-
[5]	Gamanayake et. Al.	Detection of people entering rooms	Edge-AI Application	Raspberry Pi 3 development board, Movidius-NCS	Better accuracy and latency by proposed cluster pruning method	some hyper parameter mis-specifications in the fine-tuning process is possible	304 x 304	2622 (training and validation), 786
[6]	VITTORIO MAZZIA , ALEEM KHALIQ ,	Real-Time Apple Detection	Edge AI Application	Intel Movidius Neural Computing	better results than classical L2 regularization	image registration has not been directly addressed in order to	1920x 1080	NA

	FRANCESCO SALVETTI, AND MARCELLO CHIABERGE			Stick (NCS 2)		reduce double count		
[7]	YUAN DAI et. Al.	Foreign object detection between Platform Screen Doors and metro doors	Video-sensors-based detection	Intel Core i7-6820HK CPU	YOLOv3 speed	high computational power and lack of standard dataset	600 × 480	688,296
[8]	C. -J. Chen et. Al.	Real-time image recognition	Image processing and impact map creation	DS3231 Real Time Clock, Arduino Nano, Raspber pi, SX1276 transceiver	YOLOv3 model reduces the difficulty of training deep networks	It is difficult to obtain image data of pests	52 × 52	687
[9]	MATEUSZ CHMURSKI et. Al.	Real-time operation of radar gesture classifier	Deployment on the edge device	Raspbery Pi4, NCS-2, BGT60TR13 C radar board	avoids unnecessary communication latencies and smaller memory footprint	trade-off between performance and adaptability is unavoidable	-	-
[10]	A. A. Ahmed et al.	detect moving objects in surveillance videos in real-time	Motion detection	Raspber Pi 3, NCS-2	deploying powerful machine learning models locally on the surveillance camera without cloud compute dependence	-	200 X 200	6063,2433, 1601
[11]	Larry J. Horner	Edge, edge computing in fish farm, underwater drone, ML in fabric printing, automotive	EDGE APPLICATIONS	-	bringing AI inferencing to the Edge to increase quality and improve production is a common theme	-	-	-

		manufacturing						
[12]	Sergio Bernabé et al.	Earthquake Damage detection	Classification	Intel Xeon processor and Intel Movidius NCS	portability and high performance inference	-	128 X 128	224,22,22
[13]	Owais Ali, Hazrat Ali, Syed Ayaz Ali Shah, and Aamir Shahzad	Medical	Image segmentation	NCS-2	cost-effective and portable solutions	Domain expert knowledge essential	128 X 128	59985,5890,9145
[14]	Gianluca Giuffrida et. Al.	Satellite Earth Observation	Image segmentation	EoT, powered by the Myriad 2 VPU	Compute efficiency: 600 MHz at 1 W consumption, a complete inference engine, providing a payload-compatible, host-controlled, reconfigurable, low power, low heat generation, high-speed interfaced device,	limitations on maximum intra-layer memory	192 X 192	96 000, 600, --
[15]	Weilin Yang et. Al.	Offline glass screen defects inspection	Defect classification	Intel i7-9700 (CPU), GeForce RTX 2080Ti GPU,with 11-GB graphics memories	computational speed and accuracy of YOLOv3	Defects smaller than neighbouring pixels are difficult to identify	572 x 572	280, 60, 60
[16]	Megan C. Casey et al.	Single-event effects test	Effects of irradiation on edge AI hardware	Intel NCS2, Google coral accelerator module	little impact on the majority of the accuracy metrics	USB communications failed	224 X 224	NA
[17]	CHAO DANG et al.	Real time Railway Track Damage Detection	Multiple NCS2s in a single procedure	Multi (2*NCS2) + Raspberry Pi 4B, Nvidia Jetson TK1 and Nvidia Jetson TX2	NCS and NCS2 can be plugged into any device based on Windows, Linux, MacOS, or Raspbian	-	640 X 640	1211,241,243
[18]	Panpan Zhang et. Al.	Ship detection	Image filtering	TITAN×12-GB graphics	Filtering module inspired by the filtering	-	3000 × 3000	-

				processing unit (GPU)	mechanisms of the human brain			
[19]	R. Khanam et. Al.	Industrial defect detection review	Convolutional Neural Networks	-	-	-	-	-
[20]	Peiyao Zhang et. Al.	Deep Learning-Based Tool-Tip Prediction	Real-time Model Predictive Control (MPC)	RTX 3090 GPU	less labelling effort	required micron-scale precision remains a significant surgical challenge	200 X 400	320,80